

Comparing health and environmental impacts of dental amalgam with alternative restorative materials

Historically, dental amalgam—a combination of liquid mercury and a powdered alloy of silver, tin, and copper—has been widely used for dental restorations.³ However, due to concerns over mercury's toxicity and its potential risks to human health and the environment,^{3,4} the use of amalgam has continued to decline in the last 10 years.⁵ Other direct restorative materials (e.g. resin composites and glass ionomers) are now more frequently used, but their health and environmental impacts are not yet fully understood.

This review was commissioned by the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC) prior to the Conference of the Parties to the Minamata Convention on Mercury (COP-6),⁶ aiming to support and inform decisions on the future use of dental amalgam within the UK.

This review included 215 studies: 195 studies evaluated health impacts, 21 studies evaluated environmental impacts.

Key findings included:

- ◆ The quantity of evidence directly comparing the health or environmental impacts of amalgam with other materials was limited.
- ◆ The number of non-comparative studies evaluating the impacts of amalgam or mercury far exceeded those evaluating other types of material.
- ◆ The health impact of occupational or maternal exposure was not explored for non-amalgam restorative materials.
- ◆ There were no high quality environmental studies, and very few which directly compared amalgam with another restorative material.
- ◆ Fewer than half of the studies evaluating environmental impact measured a demonstrable effect, e.g. animal toxicity or carbon footprint. The majority only reported the *potential* for environmental impact, e.g. a level of toxicity associated with restorative materials, without indicating the degree to which this would cause harm.

Dental restorations are among the most common medical procedures performed globally,¹ with dental caries (tooth decay) being one of the major reasons for direct dental restorations.^{1,2}

Final report

How did we do this review?

Finding evidence: We searched databases which included health care and environmental science journals. We conducted backwards/forwards citation chasing and checked reviews, Google Search and the HealthcareLCA (Life Cycle Assessment) database.

Eligibility criteria: Health and environmental impacts of materials used for direct dental restorations. Studies from high-income countries, published in English from 2007 onwards.

Study deprioritization: We did not quality appraise/synthesize studies: 1) Only reporting exposure outcomes not directly related to health impact, 2) Where link between dental restorative material and health impact not primary focus, 3) Of cross-sectional design with/without comparison group.

Synthesis: We narratively synthesized health impacts by grouping studies according to type of restorative material, then dividing studies by population group (where applicable) and broad health impact evaluated. Studies evaluating environmental impacts were synthesized similarly.

Research questions: What are the health and environmental impacts of direct dental restorations made of amalgam compared to other direct restorative materials?

Overview of the evidence

Dental material evaluated	N prioritised studies
Health impact	
<i>Amalgam vs Resin based composite Pa-</i>	6
<i>Amalgam only</i>	52
• Patients	36
• Dental professionals	7
• Maternal exposure	10
<i>Resin based composite</i>	16
• Dental professionals	1
• Patients	15
<i>Glass ionomer vs Composite Resin (Patients only)</i>	3
Environmental impact	
Amalgam only	11
Composite resin only	4
Multiple materials (materials included from two studies)	7*

81 studies (107 articles) were prioritised for synthesis, 61 studies evaluated health impacts, 21 evaluated environmental impacts (one study evaluated both health and environmental impacts).

Eighteen of 25 broad **health impact categories** were supported by evidence from >1 category of restorative material. The most common type of health impacts evaluated included **Allergy** (n=13), **General physical health** (n=14), **Musculoskeletal** (n=10), **Neurological** (n=13), **Neuropsychological** (n=15), **Oral health** (n=18) and **Psychosocial** (n=13).

Environmental impacts included **mercury levels** in wastewater (n=5), solid waste (n=3), emissions (n=3), vapour (n=3) and particulate matter (n=2); **monomer levels** in wastewater (n=2), particulate matter (n=1) and emissions (n=1). Demonstrable environmental impacts related to multiple restoration materials included **carbon footprint** (n=1) and **animal toxicity** (n=2).

Study quality

Health impact studies: Sixteen rated as strong quality, 18 studies as moderate and 26 studies rated as weak quality.

Environmental impact studies: Ten studies rated medium risk and 11 studies rated high risk of bias.

What did we find? - Health impacts

Amalgam vs Resin based composite	<p>Patients: Whilst few significant differences between treatment groups were observed across broad impact categories, the limited quantity of comparative evidence means we cannot be confident that there is no significant difference in health impact between amalgam and composite materials. Whilst some differences between the health impact of amalgam versus composite resin were found for neuropsychological and psychosocial symptoms, one type of restorative material was not consistently better than the other.</p>
Amalgam only	<p>Restorations in situ/restoration removal in patients (36 studies): Heterogeneity in measures of amalgam exposure/health impacts and weak quality evidence prevented firm conclusions being drawn regarding the impact of amalgam on patient health.</p> <p>Occupational exposure for health professionals (7 studies): Few consistent significant associations between mercury and health impacts found in individual health categories.</p> <p>Maternal exposure (10 studies): <i>ADHD/Autism (n=2):</i> No firm conclusions regarding association between child autism/ADHD following maternal exposure.</p> <p><i>Neuropsychological (n=3):</i> Maternal exposure may impact child overall cognitive ability with some sex differences, but study heterogeneity limits conclusions.</p> <p><i>Pregnancy impacts (n=7):</i> No association between maternal amalgam exposure and childhood death for non-occupationally exposed mothers. Further research required into miscarriage risk for individuals with higher amalgam exposure. Tentative evidence suggests no association between maternal exposure and birth malformations, but the small quantity of low quality studies limit confidence in this finding.</p>
Resin based composite only	<p>Strongest evidence focused on neuro- and/or psychological impact and stemmed from three articles associated with the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. Only a few associations were found between composite resin and performance on psychological tests and greater exposure to BisGMA-composite was linked to poorer psychosocial health at follow-up.</p>
Glass Ionomer vs RBC/ Compomer	<p>Study designs, outcomes of interest and findings were heterogeneous, precluding identification of any clear conclusions regarding which restorative material was least detrimental to health.</p>

What did we find? - Environmental impacts

All materials (21 studies)	<p>Few meaningful comparisons between different studies were possible. Even when individual studies compared two or more restorative materials, they did not always measure the relevant type of toxicity for each material.</p> <p>One study indicated composite resins are less environmentally harmful than amalgam with respect to animal toxicity, and that glass-ionomer was the least environmentally harmful.</p> <p>Only one study measured the carbon footprint of restorative materials—but crucially only measured activity associated with undertaking fillings (e.g. travel), rather than the materials themselves.</p>
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What are the implications of this review?

This systematic review aimed to inform and support decision making around the future use of dental amalgam. Key implications include:

Policy makers:

- ◇ Findings from this review may be used in conjunction with other research and discussions from the Minamata COP-6 to support UK government policy regarding future use of amalgam.

Future research:

◆ *Health impacts*

- ◇ Further high-quality research is required to fully understand the health impacts of different types of material both individually and compared to one another.
- ◇ There are comparatively fewer studies evaluating the health impacts of **resin based composite** and **glass ionomer** restorative materials across all population groups which should be addressed, particularly given current UK public health policy directing the phasing down of amalgam use.
- ◇ Further high-quality trials evaluating the potential health impacts associated with **resin based composite** would be beneficial. Particular health impacts include adverse events, cardiovascular disease, dermatological, gastrointestinal, general physical health, musculoskeletal, neurological, respiratory and visual ocular symptoms. Health impacts associated with **occupational and maternal exposure** to glass ionomer or composite resin restorations also need to be evaluated.

◆ *Environmental impacts*

- ◇ Future studies should include meaningful comparisons of the toxicity associated with amalgam and non-amalgam-based materials, specifically, mercury and monomers. This requires either using established guidance to assess whether levels of toxicity are compliant with guidance, or comparing the effects of toxicity from different restorative materials on the environment, ideally in a controlled setting.
- ◇ More studies which measure carbon emissions are needed.

Clinical practice:

- ◇ The **PPI** group for this project indicated patients would like to be kept **informed** of the potential **health** and **environmental** implications of different restorative materials and involved in the **decision-making** process.

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Journal article:

[Shaw et al., The health
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